

‘Thermo-ageing’ of Colloids. Part I. Variation of Refractivity.

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Work of a number of investigators would appear to show that a freshly prepared colloid does not represent an equilibrium condition between the micelles and the dispersion medium. Usually, the viscosity and the flocculation value, for example, in the case of fresh sols diminish and become stationary on allowing to stand. The corresponding viscosity (that is, after allowing to stand) and in numerous cases, the conductivity vary in the opposite sense. Surface tension also changes, though not always in the same direction. These are the principal facts observed during the ‘ageing’ of colloids. The interesting work of Davies (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, **33**, 274) indicates that temperature might be an important factor in this process. It is extremely likely that the nature and the size of the particles change presumably comparably to what is produced in coagulations. In the results published elsewhere in this Journal, it has been found that μ , the refractive index of a colloid, changes sensibly during coagulation. Corresponding data, distinctive of the influence of ‘ageing’ on μ , are not available in the literature of the subject. The scope of the following experiments has been restricted to changes in μ due to ‘thermo-ageing’, that is, when the colloid was allowed to stand at moderately high temperatures for definite periods. Corresponding results for ‘ageing’ at ordinary temperatures, now in the course of compilation in these laboratories, will be communicated shortly.

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

Colloidal solutions of arsenious and antimony sulphides (Joshi and Prabhu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **8**, 11, 337), manganese dioxide and ferric oxide (Joshi and Lal, *ibid.*, 1933, **10**, 61; Joshi and Nanjappa, *ibid.*, 1933, **10**, 599) were prepared and their colloid contents estimated as described previously (*loc. cit.*) in this series.

Cadmium sulphide sol was prepared by adding drop by drop concentrated ammonia to a 10 per cent. solution of cadmium sulphate, until the precipitate produced just dissolved. On saturating this with

hydrogen sulphide, a heavy precipitate and a yellow supernatant solution were obtained, which were allowed to stand overnight. The clear solution was then decanted off and the excess of hydrogen sulphide expelled by prolonged warming. The sol was then stocked in a well cleaned jena bottle, and its colloid content estimated by evaporating to dryness a suitable known volume of the sol and weighing the residue accurately.

Colloid sulphur was prepared by mixing carefully saturated solutions of hydrogen sulphide and sulphur dioxide. The excess of either of the dissolved gases was first driven out by gentle warming; the process was completed by leading a current of pure hydrogen through the colloid. Its content was estimated as in the case of colloid cadmium sulphide. Mercury sulphide sol was obtained from aqueous mercury cyanide by a method similar to that followed with colloid arsenious sulphide. Its colloid content was estimated approximately as in the last case.

Cupric oxide sol was prepared by Bredig's method with some modifications. Two stout rods of pure copper were used as electrodes, and the colloid obtained by intermittent sparking. A regularity in the frequency of this process, which was found essential in giving a stable sol with a uniform dispersion of the colloid material, was secured by mounting one of the electrodes on a firm and flexible support which vibrated by contact with the axle of a motor kept running at a uniform speed. The voltage between the electrodes was about 70 and the current about 4 amps. A very considerable amount of heat was produced, which had an instabilising action on the colloid. This was reduced to a minimum by cooling with a rapid stream of water. The colloid content was estimated by the iodometric estimation of copper in a known amount of the sol.

The aluminium hydroxide sol was prepared by the hydrolysis of a dilute solution of aluminium acetate and subsequent removal of acetic acid by careful heating as recommended by Crum (*Annalen*, 1854, 89, 156). The colloid content was obtained by the gravimetric estimation of aluminium trioxide from a known amount of the sol when treated with dilute ammonia.

Colloid thorium hydroxide was prepared by first forming a suspension of the hydroxide by treating aqueous thorium nitrate with an excess of ammonia. This was then heated nearly to the boiling point, and maintained in this condition for about seven hours with intermittent additions of small quantities of dilute

hydrochloric acid. The resulting fine opalescent sol was then purified by dialysis.

The vanadic acid sol was prepared by first making a paste of a finely powdered sample of the acid with distilled water. It was then taken up with more water in successive small additions and finally filtered through a double filter paper. The colloid content was estimated as in the case of the sulphur sol.

In preparing the copper ferrocyanide sol, solutions of about 1% copper sulphate and about 0.1% potassium ferrocyanide were mixed carefully. The resulting sol which was of a clear brown colour showed incipient coagulation after about a couple of days on standing. The refractive index measurements were, therefore, made with a fresh sample. It contained traces of potassium sulphate as an electrolytic impurity produced during the colloid formation. The colloid content was estimated after first removing the cyanide, acidifying with acetic acid and estimating the copper present iodometrically.

To a cold and freshly prepared solution of about 0.2 g of potassium ferrocyanide in 200 c.c. of water, small amounts from a solution of 0.04 g. of ferric chloride in 200 c.c. water were added with continuous stirring. The resulting sol of Prussian blue was found to be stable for at least two months. Its colloid content was estimated by an iodometric determination of its iron content as described in the previous case.

Colloid selenium was prepared by reducing with a current of sulphur dioxide, a solution containing about 0.25 g. of selenium dioxide dissolved in about 200 c.c. of warm water. The excess of sulphur dioxide was driven out completely by a careful and prolonged warming. The strength of the sol was obtained by the coagulation of a known volume of the sol.

Zsigmondy's method (*cf.* Von Weimarn, *Kolloid Z.*, 1923, 33, 81) was used for preparing colloidal silver. *N*/200-solution of silver nitrate was warmed gently with the requisite proportion of alkaline formaldehyde in dark. In estimating the colloid content, a known amount of sol is taken and dissolved by addition of concentrated nitric acid. To this was then added dilute hydrochloric acid, which precipitated silver chloride. This was filtered, washed, dried, weighed, and the corresponding amount of silver suspended in the sol calculated. Essentially the same method was used in preparing the gold sol from gold chloride. A clear and a very stable red sol was obtained. The

colloid content was estimated approximately by a gravimetric estimation of metallic gold from a known amount of the colloid.

Colloid silver chloride was prepared by adding very slowly and carefully from *N/100*-potassium chloride solution to *N/100*-silver nitrate. The resulting sol was then dialysed for about 72 hours until free from the electrolytes. The colloid was stocked in a jena container and screened from light throughout the work. The colloid content was estimated by a gravimetric estimation of silver chloride by coagulating a known amount of the sol.

The *til* and fish oil ($\mu_b = 1.4650, 1.4802$, respectively at 30°) emulsions were prepared by the precipitation method (*cf.* Joshi, *Kolloid Z.*, 1923, **34**, 197). About one c. c. of each of these oils was dissolved in a few c. c. of absolute alcohol. This was then poured in about a litre of twice distilled water which was kept boiling hot, and the mixture vigorously shaken. Excess of alcohol was removed by boiling off carefully. The emulsion was then filtered using a double filter paper of close texture and was found to be quite stable.

The refractive index measurements were first made at 30° with a Pulfrich refractometer in a manner and with precautions as described elsewhere in this Journal (1936, **13**, 141). A definite volume of the colloid was then 'thermo-aged' by boiling slowly and carefully under reflux condenser for $2\frac{1}{2}$ hours on a free flame in the majority of cases. It was then allowed to cool. The loss by evaporation of water during this period was found to be only about 0.5 c. c., which was made up by adding the necessary amount of water. It was observed, in the case of arsenious sulphide, cupric oxide, silver, silver chloride and the oil suspensions, that the boiling had a flocculating effect. In these cases the sols were 'thermo-aged' by merely heating on a water-bath for the above period. Refractive index in all the cases was redetermined at 30° . Every observation was repeated at least twice using different samples of the colloid and fully reproducible results were obtained. The concentration of the colloid was varied at least by half in every case. These results are given in the tables.

TABLE I.

Colloid.	Colloid content.	μ_1 before heating.	μ_2 after heating.	Change in μ .
Mercuric sulphide	0.3 g./litre	1.33214	1.33221	0.00007
	0.2	1.33214	1.33221	0.00007
Antimony sulphide	2.1	1.33214	1.33221	0.00007
	1.05	1.33206	1.33214	0.00008

TABLE I (contd.).

Colloid.	Colloid content.	μ_1 before heating.	μ_2 after heating.	Change in μ .
Arsenious sulphide	6.6 g./litre.	1.33487	1.33495	0.00008
	1.8	1.33260	1.33268	0.00008
Cadmium sulphide	2.2	1.33206	1.33214	0.00008
	1.1	1.33206	1.33214	0.00008
Sulphur hydrosol	0.15	1.33175	1.33183	0.00008
Manganese dioxide	2.50	1.33214	1.33221	0.00007
	1.25	1.33214	1.33221	0.00007
Cupric oxide	0.85	1.33260	1.33268	0.00008
	0.30	1.33198	1.33206	0.00008
Ferric hydroxide	1.2	1.33268	1.33276	0.00008
	0.9	1.33268	1.33276	0.00008
Aluminium hydroxide	1.2	1.33299	1.33307	0.00008
	0.8	1.33291	1.33299	0.00008
	0.3	1.33284	1.33299	0.00015
Thorium hydroxide	5	1.33206	1.33214	0.00008
	2.5	1.33198	1.33214	0.00016
	1.25	1.33191	1.33206	0.00015
Vanadic acid	1.1	1.33214	1.33221	0.00007
	0.5	1.33206	1.33214	0.00008
	0.37	1.33206	1.33214	0.00008
Prussian blue	3.0 (as Fe)	1.33487	1.33495	0.00008
	0.6 (as Fe)	1.33291	1.33299	0.00008
Copper ferrocyanide	0.4 (as Cu)	1.33260	1.33268	0.00008
	0.2 (as Cu)	1.33260	1.33268	0.00008
Selenium	0.8	1.33214	1.33221	0.00007
	0.6	1.33214	1.33221	0.00007
Silver hydrosol	0.3	1.33206	1.33214	0.00008
	0.15	1.33198	1.33206	0.00008
Gold hydrosol		1.33214	1.33221	0.00007
		1.33206	1.44214	0.00008
Silver chloride	1.25	1.33260	1.33268	0.00008
	1.0	1.33253	1.33260	0.00007
	0.75	1.33245	1.33253	0.00008
	0.5	1.33328	1.33253	0.00015
TII oil emulsion	C	1.33184	1.33191	0.00007
	C/2	1.33184	1.33191	0.00007
Fish oil emulsion	C ₁	1.33198	1.33206	0.00008
	C _{1/4}	1.33198	1.33206	0.00008

DISCUSSION.

Since sols were 'thermo-aged' by boiling, except when this produced a sensible instabilisation of the colloid, it would appear that at least two factors are involved, *viz.*, (i) a pure temperature effect, which is probably mainly fundamental to 'thermo-ageing' and (ii) accessory mechanical effects such as the breaking of the air-liquid interface, convection currents, etc., attendant upon ebullition. On the whole, these latter would appear to be analogous to the possible influence of shaking, stirring etc., on the coagulation of colloids (Smoluchowski, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1917, **92**, 155, *et al*; Freundlich and Basu, *ibid.*, 1925, **118**, 203; Freundlich and Kroch, *ibid.*, 1928, **129**, 368; Freundlich, 'Colloid and Capillary Chemistry,' 1926, p. 439; Joshi and Narayan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc. Ray Comm. Vol.*, 1933, pp. 41—52; Joshi and Iyengar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 573). On general grounds, one would anticipate that stirring would accelerate coagulation, presumably chiefly by increasing the frequency of micellar collisions. A review of the literature (*vide supra*) shows, however, that this anticipation is not always realised in practice. Works of Freundlich and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) and of Joshi and Iyengar (*loc. cit.*) show that the accelerating influence of stirring obtains only when it is vigorous and at moderate and higher concentrations of coagulating electrolytes. As regards these effects in the absence of any coagulating electrolytes, no data appear to exist in the literature.

The foregoing results show that in every one of the 42 cases of the nineteen sols examined, μ , the refractive index of the colloid is increased sensibly as a result of 'thermo-ageing'. This suggests the production of a common change so as to vary μ in the same sense in all the cases. A diminution of the particle-size due to thermo-ageing would appear to be a simple and plausible explanation of this phenomenon on general grounds. The refractivity of a colloidal solution depends upon the total length of the optical path which a given beam of light traverses while passing through the system. This would depend upon the refractive index of the colloid material, that of the continuous medium, the size (presumably the shape), the electrical charge of the particles and their ionic atmosphere. Of this, no general theory is available in the literature. Working out of particular consequences in relation to observed facts and the assumptions implied in the derivation would appear to be

both legitimate and suggestive of further work. An increased dispersion of the colloid, that is, a diminution of the particle-size, for example, would increase the proportion of the colloid matter in the optical path; it would, therefore, bring μ nearer to that characteristic of the dispersed phase, that is, increase it, since the refractive index of any of the suspended materials is greater than that of the dispersion medium (μ_0 for water = 1.33204 at 30°). The observed influence on μ of 'thermo-ageing' is in agreement with this deduction. It is to be anticipated that a main result of the diminution of the micellar size will be an increase in the corresponding charge and therefore, the stability of the colloid. In this connection it is interesting to point out some of the results of Davies (*loc. cit.*) on the electrolytic coagulation of gold sols, which had been subjected previously to 'thermo-ageing'. He observed that when the sol was 'thermo-aged' for moderate periods and then mixed with electrolytes, the coagulation velocity diminished with the duration of 'thermo-ageing' which shows that the stability of the sol increased during the process. The reverse effect was also observed when 'thermo-ageing' was prolonged. This is to be expected since the frequency and intensity of collisions increase with temperature, which favour micellar coalescence. It must, however, be pointed out that the above considerations regarding the dependence of μ on the only factor treated, *viz.*, the particle-size are not without limitations of applicability. It has been found for example in the data for μ during coagulations reported elsewhere in this Journal (*loc. cit.*) that *while in the majority of the coagulations studied, μ diminished during the change, sufficiently numerous cases have been observed (ibid.) showing just the reverse effect.* Furthermore, the diminution of the coagulation rate at any rate in some cases of the thermo-aged sols examined by Davies (*loc. cit.*) might not inconceivably be due to reduction in the number of micells in unit volume, which might be brought about by an increase in the average particle-size due to coalescence during 'thermo-ageing'. In the absence of a comprehensive general theory of the refractivity of a colloid in terms of the relevant factors mentioned already, which can correlate these results, accumulation of more experimental data for μ under diverse conditions of micellar behaviour is the principal need of the present phase of the development of the subject.